

CRNN-Based Frame-Level Respiratory Phase Segmentation from Breathing Audio

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Abstract—Respiratory phase segmentation from audio enables non-invasive pulmonary monitoring but is challenged by variability, noise, and ambiguous phase boundaries. This work proposes a compact convolutional recurrent neural network (CRNN) for frame-level classification of inhalation, exhalation, and pause using log-mel spectrograms. The model combines spectro-temporal feature learning with temporal modeling and is trained using a class-imbalance-aware objective that integrates focal loss and label-smoothed cross entropy. A subject-wise evaluation protocol is adopted to ensure generalization. The approach achieves robust and stable performance, demonstrating its effectiveness for respiratory sound analysis.

Index Terms—Respiratory Sound Analysis, Breathing Phase Segmentation, Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Respiratory sound analysis provides a practical approach for non-invasive pulmonary assessment [1], [2]. However, accurate phase segmentation is difficult due to non-stationary acoustics, inter-subject variability, and ambiguous transitions [3]. Traditional methods rely on handcrafted features and thresholds, limiting generalization.

Deep learning models, particularly convolutional recurrent neural network (CRNN), enable joint modeling of spectral and temporal information. This work addresses class imbalance and boundary uncertainty through a compact architecture and a task-aware training strategy with subject-wise evaluation.

II. METHODOLOGY

This work studied 71 (9-28 s) intraoral respiratory audio recordings from the DPI-Watch: An Inhaler Sound Dataset available from Zenodo, an open research repository [4].

Respiratory audio is resampled, band-pass filtered (100–1500 Hz), normalized, and denoised to enhance signal representation [1]. Log-mel spectrograms are extracted to provide frame-level time-frequency features.

The CRNN consists of convolutional layers for feature learning and bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) layers for temporal modeling. In this work, frame-level predictions are generated using a softmax layer [5]. To address class imbalance and uncertainty near phase boundaries, the

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Fig. 1. Sample respiratory waveform with predicted I: inhalation (blue), E: exhalation (red), and C: pause (gray) phases.

training objective combines focal loss with label-smoothed cross-entropy. The model is optimized using the AdamW optimizer with early stopping and learning rate scheduling. A subject-wise data partitioning strategy is used to prevent data leakage and ensure realistic evaluation.

III. RESULTS

The model achieves strong performance with a macro F1-score of approximately 0.94 under subject-wise evaluation. Precision and recall remain balanced across inhale and exhale, with high accuracy, also for the pause class.

The model produces temporally consistent predictions aligned with respiratory cycles (Fig. 1). Errors mainly occur in low-energy transition regions due to inherent ambiguity.

A deidentified retrospective (sub)dataset from D-BEST Lab (Purdue University IRB #2023-1889) with 20, 7–20 s intraoral breathing sound recordings was used for cross-dataset generalization evaluation. The CRNN achieved an F1-score of 0.84, indicating slight performance drop on unseen data.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a CRNN-based approach for frame-level respiratory phase segmentation with robust performance, supporting downstream breathing sounds analysis pipelines for scalable non-contact respiratory monitoring [2], [6], [7].

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